

Studies in 1-Aza-1,3-butadienes. Reaction of Acid Anhydrides with Open-Chain Conjugated Azomethines

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Reactions of acetic, maleic, succinic and phthalic anhydrides with conjugated azomethines (I) have been described. Substituents in the ortho position of the amine offer steric hindrance. Electron-donating functions in the amine moiety facilitate the reaction. Addition of the anhydride molecule to the carbon-nitrogen double bond appears to take place prior to hydrolysis to yield the anilides and the aldehyde.

AZOMETHINES are known to react with anhydrides giving additional products that may be hydrolysed to give the acid amides and the corresponding carbonyl compounds¹⁻⁵. Benzylidene anilines in solvents or on fusion with succinic and phthalic anhydrides are also known to yield half acid amides⁶. We wish to report here the reaction of a few anhydrides with 1-aza-1,3-butadiene derivatives (I) prepared from *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde and substituted anilines with the object of studying the effect of substituents in the aniline moiety on the ease of formation of anilides.

o-Nitrocinnamaldehyde was obtained by the nitration of freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde in acetic anhydride with nitric acid at 0°-5°. Azomethines⁷ (I) were synthesized by condensing it with substituted anilines using a 'Dean and Stark' water separator in dry benzene, or ethyl alcohol at room temperature. These nitro

substituted 1-aza-1,3-butadienes have been made to react with anhydrides of acetic, maleic, succinic and phthalic acids. The addition products from these azomethines and anhydrides could not be isolated as these are very unstable and decompose spontaneously,

probably due to the presence of a strongly electron-withdrawing nitro group in the ortho position of the anils, to yield the parent *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde and the corresponding anilides in good yields. While the rate of decomposition could not be studied in detail, an idea of the ease of formation of the anilides was obtained by the amount of anilides separated out at different intervals of time (Table 1). It was observed that with electron-releasing group in the aniline moiety, the reaction was faster as in case of I (X=CH₃, OMe, OEt). The reverse is true for electron-withdrawing substituents, e. g. nitro group. The reaction was almost suppressed in the case of 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene and the compound was recovered unchanged (90%) even after two months. Steric hindrance also appeared to play a significant role in diminishing the reactivity of ortho substituted anilines. Thus 1-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene gave very poor yield of the anilide. The electronic effect on these reactions is in agreement with the following mechanism in which the first step is the formation of an adduct (II). The latter then undergoes hydrolysis under the reaction

TABLE 1—(X-C₆H₄-NHCOCH₃)

S. No.	X=	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)	Time taken for the precipitation of the product.
1.	-H	78	114	24 hrs.
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	30	112	7 days.
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	75	154	24 hrs.
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	80	130	12 hrs.
5.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	90	135	12 hrs.
6.	<i>p</i> -OH	70	150	2 days.
7.	<i>m</i> -Cl	68	79	2 days.
8.	<i>p</i> -Cl	70	179	3 days.
9.	<i>p</i> -Br	65	167	3 days.
10.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	30	155	10 days.

conditions. Thus when X is electron releasing, the C=N bond becomes more nucleophilic and undergoes addition to the anhydride at a fast rate. On the contrary, if hydrolysis was the first step, then such substituents

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would be expected to retard the reaction with water. The steric effect would also be difficult to understand.

Reaction of pure maleic anhydride with these azomethines in dry chloroform was faster and yielded only the half acid amides by the hydrolysis of the adducts.

These half-acid amides have been characterized by their elemental analysis, mixed melting point determination and infrared spectra in some cases. Data for these amides are recorded in the Table 2.

The mother liquor on dilution with water deposited *o*-nitro-cinnamaldehyde which was recrystallised from ethanol to give 1.41 g of the pure compound in 80% yield, m.p. 127°–128°.

2. To a 50 ml flask containing 1-phenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene (2.52 g, 0.01 mole), was added freshly distilled (AR grade) acetic anhydride (10 ml). The mixture was warmed at 120° for 2 hr. The excess of anhydride was then removed *in vacuo* to yield a red coloured syrup that failed to crystallize. This syrup when allowed to stand in open for 24 hr.

TABLE 2—X.C₆H₄NHCOCH—CH₂.COOH

S. No.	X=	Yield	M.P.* °C	Formula	Elemental Found%	Analysis Calcd. %	IR Spectra (cm ⁻¹)
1.	-H	80	203	C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₃	N 7.3	7.3	3272, 3200 (NH) 1718—1698 (CO)
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	88	199	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₃	N 6.7	6.8	3280, 3200 (NH) 1698 (CO)
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	90	175	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₄	N 6.1	6.3	3260 (NH), 1710 (CO)
4.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	100	185	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₄	N 5.8	5.9	—
5.	<i>o</i> -OH	20	189	C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₄	N 6.7	6.7	3575 (OH) 3380, 3200 (NH) 1720 (CO)
6.	<i>p</i> -OH	68	192	C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₄	N 6.7	6.7	—
7.	<i>m</i> -Cl	65	195	C ₁₀ H ₈ NO ₃ Cl	N 6.0 Cl 15.9	6.2 15.7	—
8.	<i>p</i> -Cl	65	187	C ₁₀ H ₈ NO ₃ Cl	C 53.3 H 3.6 N 6.7 Cl 15.1	53.3 3.5 6.2 15.7	—
9.	<i>p</i> -Br	55	193	C ₁₀ H ₈ NO ₃ Br	N 5.0 Br 29.4	5.1 29.5	—
10.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	50	199	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O ₅	N 11.5	11.8	3272 (NH), 1700 (CO)
11.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	58	193	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ O ₅	C 50.2 H 3.3 N 11.8	50.8 3.4 11.8	—

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

Similar products are obtained from the reaction of purified succinic and phthalic anhydrides with these azomethines. It might be noted that the water necessary for the conversion of the adducts into anilides apparently came from air or reagents.

Experimental

Reaction of 1-Aza-1, 3-butadienes with Acetic Anhydride :

1. Into a 25 ml conical flask containing 1-phenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene (2.52 g, 0.01 mole), was added freshly distilled (AR grade) acetic anhydride (5 ml). The flask was stoppered and allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hr. The thick syrup thus obtained when placed in a beaker over-night yielded a crystalline product which was recrystallized from ethanol to give acetanilide (1.01 g, in 78% yield), m.p. 114°.

deposited crude acetanilide which was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol to give the pure compound (1.0 g, 75% yield), m.p. 114°.

The reaction of other azomethines with acetic anhydride, except 1-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene and 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene which failed to react, similarly yielded the corresponding anilides and *o*-nitro-cinnamaldehyde.

Reaction of 1-Aza-1, 3-butadienes with Maleic Anhydride : Into a 50 ml conical flask containing 1-phenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene (2.52g, 0.01 mole) taken in dry chloroform (20 ml) was added freshly resublimed maleic anhydride (0.98g, 0.01 mole). The reaction occurred spontaneously just on warming and a compound separated out. After cooling the reaction mixture in ice, the product was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol to provide cream coloured needles of maleanilic acid (1.52 g, 80%), m.p. 203°.

The mother liquor on evaporation and recrystallization from ethanol yielded *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde quantitatively, m.p. 126°-128°.

These compounds showed no depression in mixed melting points with authentic samples.

Other azomethines except 1-*o*-tolyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene that failed to react, behaved similarly.

Reaction of 1-Aza-1, 3-butadienes with Phthalic Anhydride : 1-Phenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene (2.52 g, 0.01 mole), phthalic anhydride (1.48 g, 0.01 mole) were heated under reflux for 30 min in chloroform (25 ml) in a 100 ml flask fitted with a reflux condenser. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the crystals which separated out, were filtered at the pump. On recrystallization from ethanol the crude product gave white needles of amidic acid (2.0 g, 85% yield), m.p. 164°-166°. From the mother liquor (chloroform) was obtained *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde in quantitative yield, m.p. 126°-127°.

Similarly the reaction of phthalic anhydride with 1-*p*-ethoxy-phenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl - 1-aza - 1,3-butadiene and 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene yielded the half acid amides m.p. 204° (90% yield) and m.p. 187° (60%) respectively in addition to *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde m.p. 126°-128° in 100% and 70% yield respectively.

Reaction of Succinic Anhydride with 1-Aza-1,3-butadienes : 1-Phenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1, 3-butadiene (2.52 g, 0.01 mole) was taken into a 100 ml RB flask fitted with a reflux condenser containing chloroform (25 ml) and freshly recrystallized succinic anhydride (1.00 g, 0.01 mole). The reaction mixture was gently warmed under reflux for 1 hr. Work-up as above provided the half acid amide as a white crystalline compound m.p. 148° in quantitative yield and *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde m.p. 127°-128° quantitatively.

Similar reaction of this anhydride with 1-*p*-ethoxy-phenyl - 4-*o*-nitrophenyl - 1-aza-1,3-butadiene yielded quantitatively the half acid amide, m.p. -165°-166° and *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde m.p. 127°-128°. The corresponding reaction of 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene yielded the amide m.p. 187°-188° in 80% yield and the aldehyde m.p. 126°-127° in 70% yield.

References

1. F. BERGMANN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2811.
2. H. R. SNYDER, R. B. HASBROUK and J. F. RICHARDSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3558.
3. H. R. SNYDER and J. C. ROBINSON JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3279.
4. B. I. ARDASHEV and Z. D. MARKOVA, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1951, 21, 1505, *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, 46, 5005.
5. H. S. ANGEL and A. R. DAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3874.
6. R. I. GEORGESCU, *Bull. Chim. Soc. Romane Chim.* 1937-1938, 39, 115; *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 5066.
7. N. SINGH and K. KRISHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973 50, 277.